

The archive of Professor Georgi Zlatarski – knowledge source of the foundation of geology and paleontology in Bulgaria

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Abstract. This paper presents a part of the documents, which are stored in the personal archive of Professor Georgi Zlatarski at the Department of University Archive of Sofia University (Bulgaria). This valuable treasure embodies not only the development of geology in Bulgaria, but also the path of a brilliant scientist towards the realization of the plans he shared in 1880 in a letter to Prof. Konstantin Irechek: “to divide Bulgaria in separate parts and to study each one in detail”; to “make a precise geological map”, and to “arrange and systematize the collection of Bulgarian fossils”. At the end of his not very long life, it can be seen that Prof. Zlatarski succeeded in realizing his plans. In 2022, a joint project between the Faculty of Geology and Geography and the Department of University Archive, which aimed to promote the archival heritage of this eminent scientist, was carried out. With the help of geologists and paleontologists, some of the document annotations were revised to define more accurately certain documents or scientific studies. After the revision, the archive is at a higher scientific level, as it includes precise terms in geology and paleontology, making it more understandable and accessible to specialists in these fields. The chronological limits of some of the undated documents were also specified. A permanent exposition of documents on the websites of the University Archive and the Faculty of Geology and Geography, as well as a presentation on the scientific career of Prof. Zlatarski, which will be used in teaching, will soon be available.

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INTRODUCTION

For each university, it is an honor to own collections of documents of its most distinguished professors and researchers. The archives of some of the oldest and most prestigious universities in Europe and USA own a priceless treasure of documents of scientists who have achieved great scientific advances and have even changed our concept of the world. Thanks to modern technology, a big part of these documents is available to scientists and researchers around the world. Most of this research has already lost its scientific value, due to the constant develop-

ment of science, but readers are always excited to be able to have a look at it.

One of the main missions of the Sofia University Archive is to seek and conserve collections of documents and personal archives of distinguished university scientists. As these professors have spent their whole lives and careers at the University, their personal archives contain many documents that are not part of the official university documentation and that help us put together the pieces about the state of the University in a certain time period or as a whole. The preserved lectures, syllabus, studies, inexhaustible correspondence, especially with foreign scien-

tists and scientific institutions, give a complete look to the history of the University and the evolution of different branches of science. A great example is the personal archive of the first Bulgarian geologist, and also one of the first university professors, Prof. Georgi Zlatarski. This article presents a part of Prof. G. Zlatarski's scientific legacy held in the Sofia University Archive Department.

REVIEW OF PREVIOUS ARCHIVISTS' WORK

The officials at the Sofia University Archive did not intentionally seek the documents of Prof. G. Zlatarski as is the usual practice. The documents of university professors who lived and worked in the first half of the existence of the University are usually tracked down and collected by the Scientific Archive of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (SA-BAS) as they were also members of the Academy. This campaign started in the 1950s. Thanks to the efforts made by BAS archivists, a great deal of documents that belonged to many of the professors who shaped the image of the University and who built the foundation of teaching various sciences in Bulgaria has been preserved. In the mid-1950s, Prof. Zlatarski's two daughters donated his letters and photographs that were filed in the Scientific Archive of BAS, under fund 71, which contains 42 archival units. In 1989, the Central State Archives (CSA) received some of Prof. Zlatarski's documents as over 240 documents were bought from an antiquarian. They were filed under fund 1834 K, but both the inventory of the documents and the documents themselves are missing. It turned out that they were yielded for processing and later lost at the Central State Archives (according to informal information from CSA experts). Information about Prof. Georgi Zlatarski can also be found in his personal files at Sofia University. The latter are stored in CSA–Sofia (fund 944 K, inventory 2, archival unit 249) and contain documents, such as his appointment to the University, orders for missions abroad, death certificate, as well as many telegrams expressing condolences received by the University after the professor's passing.

RECENT ACTIVITIES

In 2013, the then-Dean of the Faculty of Geology and Geography, Prof. Marin Ivanov, made a proposition to the University Archive to process and preserve the documents of Prof. Zlatarski, which were donated to the Faculty in 2010 by his grandsons:

Prof. Georgi and Vasil Zlatarski. In this case, there was a controversy of the principle of indivisibility of the archival collection, since the first receipt of documents was collected by the SA-BAS, and the second one by the CSA. We followed the will of the donors, who wished that the documents would be stored precisely in Sofia University, as this way they would be easily accessed by the scientists – geologists and paleontologists. Due to being improperly stored for an extensive period of time, the physical condition of the documents was not very good. In addition, according to the professor's heirs, the documents were stored for decades in the attic of the family house. The scientific and technical processing of this valuable donation started immediately in the University Archive. During the review and the initial grouping of the documents, we were able to reconstruct and put together numerous lectures and research documents that were scattered and displaced over the years, divided in different piles and papers without any logical sequence. After comparing handwriting, deciphering texts, etc., in the University Archive, we were able to restore the original form of the majority of them, and thus preserve and present the birth of geology and paleontology in Bulgaria. When processing this personal archive, we consulted multiple times the geologist Prof. Marin Ivanov, so we could correctly present the documents, which are a real treasure for the University Archive. The processing was finished in the autumn of 2014. The fund contains 322 documents and they are grouped in 270 archival units. It is filed under number 31 in the University Archive. Direct access to the inventory of documents is available on the University Archive website (https://www.uni-sofia.bg/index.php/bul/universitet_t/administraciya/ot-del_universitetski_arhiv/universitetski_arhiv/opisi_na_dokumentii2/fond_31_prof_georgi_nikolov_zlatarski_1854_1909).

THE LEGACY OF PROFESSOR GEORGI ZLATARSKI IN THE SOFIA UNIVERSITY ARCHIVE

Biographical notes

Professor Georgi Nikolov Zlatarski was born on January 25, 1854, in Veliko Tarnovo. In 1876, he graduated from high school in his hometown, and the same year he enrolled in the brand new "Natural sciences" program in the University of Zagreb. After he graduated from the University of Zagreb in 1880, he returned to Bulgaria and was appointed as a state geologist-mineralogist, a position that was

created by the Bulgarian Government especially for him. His job was to research the minerals in Bulgaria and to study the country's geological structure. Between 1880 and 1894, Georgi Zlatarski carried out this mission, being appointed to various positions in different ministries depending on the structure of the government. As the first and last holder of this position, Zlatarski manifested himself not only as a researcher, but also as an organizer of the first geological field trips in Bulgaria and abroad.

The teaching in geology at the Higher School in Sofia (this is what Sofia University was named, from its establishment in 1888 until 1904) started in 1891, in then the Department of Physics and Mathematics (from 1893, the departments became faculties). During the first few years, the professor in the department was Bone Baev, but after his death in 1894, the Academic Council invited Georgi Zlatarski as a deputy professor in geology. He accepted, seeing the opportunity to devote himself to scientific rather than administrative work, and a few months later he was appointed Associate Professor. On April 15, 1897, Georgi Zlatarski became a Full Professor and Head of the Department of Geology and Paleontology. In the Higher School, Prof. Zlatarski was a lecturer of the following courses: General Geology, Historical Geology, Geology of Bulgaria, Paleontology of Invertebrates, Physiographic and Dynamic Geology, Geotectonics and Stratigraphic Geology, Paleozoology, Introduction to Geology and Dynamic Geology. Very soon after his appointment as a full professor, Georgi Zlatarski was also elected Rector of the Higher School for the academic year 1897/1898. He was elected for a second term as rector for the year 1901/02, and in 1903/1904 he was Dean of the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics. Prof. Zlatarski was a member of the Bulgarian Literary Society (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences), founder and president of the Bulgarian Naturalistic Society, the Bulgarian Agricultural Society and many other European academies and geological associations. The studies and overall work of Prof. Zlatarski marked one of the most remarkable epochs of geology in Bulgaria, and this has repeatedly been emphasized by his followers and biographers (*e.g.*, Lacroix, 1910; Bakalov, 1955; Bonchev, 1979; Vassileff, 1982; Tzankov, 1994; Nikolov, 2004; Machev, 2014; Nachev, 2014; Tchoumatchenco and Nikolov, 2016). In his education, attitude and determination, he was a "citizen of Europe" who was equally deeply respected in his own country and by his European fellows. He died on August 9, 1909, in Veliko Tarnovo.

Main groups of archival files

The University archive stores a rich collection of documents of Prof. Georgi Zlatarski, which allow to reconstruct his whole scientific career, which in turn shows the birth of geology in Bulgaria. The documents were organized in separate sections, according to the archival requirements, for processing of personal archives. The classification scheme consists of four sections: 1) Biographical materials; 2) Officiary; 3) Scientific and research activity; and 4) Other materials. The biographical materials contain his notes, and the layout of archival units was preserved as it was left by G. Zlatarski. In his personal fund, there are documents that have one topic on one side of the sheet, and text on another topic on the other side of the same sheet. To take notes, G. Zlatarski also used envelopes, invitations, and others. The description of the archival units indicates the archival unit of the text on the back of the sheet. The majority of the documents are not dated and the date was placed later in the processing, using indirect information.

Biographical materials section

The Biographical materials section lacks documents that would help trace the lifetime of Prof. Zlatarski. The biographies, autobiographies, personal documents, diplomas, certificates, which are usual for most personal archives and would allow to obtain some information about his scientific career, are missing. Therefore, after processing the personal archive, we searched for published photographs and articles about his life and career and we included them in this section. Original documents from the legatees that are included in this section are some notebooks with notes in Croatian (from his studies at the University of Zagreb), a few letters from relatives, as well as some notes and receipts for domestic or financial matters. In accordance with the archival requirements, the documents and materials from the joint exhibition by the University Library and the University Archive, devoted to the 160th anniversary of Prof. G. Zlatarski that was held at the University and later at the "Earth and Man" Museum, were also added to this section.

Officiary section

The Officiary section is divided into subsections, which sequentially show the activities of Prof. Zlatarski as a state geologist-mineralogist, rector and professor.

A few documents from his time as a state geologist are preserved, related to the first developed coal mine in Bulgaria, the Moshino mine (present-day Pernik mines). The charts of the mines in Bulgaria made by him, and the list of mineral springs in the Sofia and Pazardzhik areas that contains the temperature, as well as the properties of the water, are of interest in this section. In 1880, G. Zlatarski accompanied the Viennese Professor Franz Toula during his second trip in Bulgaria. The field trip took

place in NW Bulgaria and they studied the stratigraphy of the Berkovitsa–Belogradchik–Vidin region. In the archive of Zlatarski (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 119*), there are around 250 sheets of paper from this first trip that contain notes about fossil findings in the region. In the same year, G. Zlatarski examined the Samokov area to study the possibilities of recovery and modernization of iron ore mining. A notebook from this field trip is preserved, which contains studies on the deposits of

Fig. 1. Section of the Lower Cretaceous strata near Veliko Tarnovo (a), field descriptions and determinations of ammonites from the areas of Veliko Tarnovo and Targovishte (b, c) made by Prof. Zlatarski during a field trip in 1882 (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 105, 117*).

salt water, salt, gypsum and coal in the areas of Veliko Tarnovo, Sofia, Pernik, Samokov and the Iskar River Gorge (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 87). There are also numerous notebooks, separate notes and writings that contain descriptions of fossils and geological observations from his field trip in 1882, in the areas of Etropole, Pleven, Veliko Tarnovo, Gabrovo, Ruse, Razgrad, Targovishte, Shumen, Varna and Silistra (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 105, 112, 114–118, 121, 127, 154) (Fig. 1). In addition, the personal archive contains many more notebooks, pocket books, separate sheets with field trip notes, fossil and geological descriptions from the years spent as state geologist. They represent his systematical efforts to study the geology of Bulgaria. Many notes that contain geological bibliography, summaries and translations of articles and works of foreign scientists (geologists and paleontologists), which helped him with his own research, were also preserved.

Scientific research and teaching section

As a result of the research in the three years prior, in 1883 G. Zlatarski published four works under the

joint title *Materials on the Geology and Mineralogy of Bulgaria*, the drafts for which are preserved in the University Archive (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 133).

In 1884, Prof. G. Zlatarski and Prof. Franz Toula went again on a joint field trip in the Central Stara Planina Mts. A notebook of a hundred pages and a pocket book that contains around 70 pages of observations, entitled by him “Geological notes from Central Bulgaria”, are preserved from this trip (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 88, 89). From the next field trip of Prof. Zlatarski, in 1886, which was focused on the geology of South Bulgaria, were preserved documents that contain petrographic descriptions, field notes on the Srednogorie region and Stara Zagora area, a terrain map, geological profile of the Haskovo region, and others (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 91–93, 106, 107) (Fig. 2). The result of this research was his work *Geological Studies in the North of the Balkan Between the Iskar and Yantra Rivers*. The manuscript of this study is also stored in the University Archive (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 133). A note on the text indicates that it was reviewed during a session of the Vienna

Fig. 2. Field notes of Prof. Zlatarski (1886) on the Srednogorie region (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 93).

Academy of Science in 1886 and submitted for publication in an Austrian scientific journal.

Other materials section

In 1895, Georgi Zlatarski became part of the small academic community of the Higher School in Sofia, and soon after he was elected rector for the year 1897/1898. That must have worried the newly elected professor, as the archive contains a draft of a letter to the Minister of Education, in which he informed the Minister that he had been elected Rector and shared his concern that administrative work might be an obstacle to his teaching and research activities. There is no information as to whether this letter was sent or not, but it is indicative of his desire to devote himself to scientific rather than administrative work. From this term as rector, there are preserved documents, such as his rector speech “Traits of the paleogeography of Bulgaria” (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 38*)

(Fig. 3), drafts of letters and a notebook with notes for the Academic Council, as well as other administrative matters of the Higher School (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 42*).

One of the letters of Prof. Zlatarski is presented herein, as it is a chrestomathian example of how important it is for the documents of Sofia University and its professors to be precisely kept in the University archive and to be processed by university archivists. While processing the archive, a draft of a letter from G. Zlatarski, which he wrote as rector and the recipient was unknown, was found. The letter contains numerous scratches; it was hard to read the text, sometimes it is in very small handwriting; the intention was to find correct and considerate phrases. After much effort to decipher and arrange the mixed-up lines, without mentioning a name, it suddenly became clear who the recipient was. I remembered that years ago, while reading the protocols of the Academic Council, I came across the proposal made by some professors to find the

Fig. 3. Title page of Prof. Zlatarski’s academic speech “Traits of the paleogeography of Bulgaria”, read on November 8, 1897, before the assembly of professors and students of the Higher School, on the occasion of his election as rector for the academic year 1897/1898 (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 38*).

archive of the former Governor-General of Eastern Rumelia Gavril Krastevich. The motive for this was that Krastevich was very old and might pass away, and he had a valuable archive that could be dispersed after his death. The importance of this archive was presented in another study, but this example highlights how important it is for the personal documents to be processed in university archives, since university archivists have information and detailed knowledge of the University matters that are unavailable to those of the State Archives, who process various types of documents and archives.

There are no documents in the archive of Georgi Zlatarski, either from his next term as rector or from his term as Dean of the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics. The collection of documents from his teaching is more substantial. This makes it possible to trace the beginnings of teaching in geology and

paleontology at Sofia University. Here is probably the first syllabus in geology, which was made by G. Zlatarski, with a timetable by semesters and classes (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 46*) (Fig. 4). There are some notes, as well as a notebook that contains the schedule for the summer semester of the year 1902/1903 with notes on what he should show the students during the lecture and others regarding the organization of the teaching process (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 44–46*). Here is also his report on the election of Georgi Bonchev as a professor, who took over the mineralogy and petrography courses (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 47*).

The lectures prepared by G. Zlatarski and presented to the students in geology are also of great interest in this collection. He wrote on the title page of the lectures in pencil the date when read and that

Предметен по Геология

- 1) Физикогеографска и динамическа Геология
- 2) Метаморфоза
- 3) Углеродна Геология
- 4) Геология на България
- 5) Палеонтология

Разпределение на преподаването:

Обща Геология (Физикогеографска и динамическа Геология) по 4 часа седмично в V и VI семестри

Палеонтология по 2 часа седмично в V и VI семестри
Екзертуми само в VI сем.

Метаморфоза по 1 час седмично в VII сем.

Углеродна Геология изобщо и свързано с България по 3 часа седмично в VII сем. + Семинари 2 + прак. работ. 2

Углеродна Геология etc. по 4 часа седмично VIII сем. + 2 семинари + 2 прак. работ. + Екзертум

V Семестър	VI Семестър	VII Сем.	VIII Сем.
Физикогеографска и динамическа Геология 4 часа Палеонтология 2 часа	Физикогеографска и динамическа Геология 4 часа Палеонтология 2 часа Екзертуми	Метаморфоза 1ч. Углеродна Геология 3 Семинари 2 практик. работ. 2	Углеродна Геология 4 часа Семинари 2 часа практик. работ. 2ч. Екзертум

Fig. 4. Probably the first study program in geology, which was made by G. Zlatarski, with a timetable by semesters and classes (*University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 46*).

Fig. 7. Draft of an unpublished Atlas of Paleontology, containing drawings and notes on the structure of various classes of invertebrates (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 132).

versity Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 135); *The Upper Cretaceous Series in Central and Western Bulgaria, North of the Balkan Range* (in Bulgarian, 1905) (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 136); *La série éocretacée ou le crétacé inférieur en Bulgarie* (in Bulgarian, with French summary, 1907) (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 143); and *The Senonian Stage in Eastern Bulgaria, North of the Balkan and its Subdivision Into Lower (Emscherien) and Upper (Aturien) Substages* (in Bulgarian, 1907) (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 144). Manuscripts prepared for publication are also extremely valuable: *Le système jurassique en Bulgarie* (in Bulgarian, with French summary, 1908) (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 137–140) (Fig. 6); *La série miocène en Bulgarie* (in Bulgarian, with French summary, 1908) (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 145, 146); *Le système triassique en Bulgarie* (in Bulgarian, with French summary, 1907) (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival units 147, 148); and other studies in geology and paleontology. Also preserved is the manuscript of a finished *Textbook or Course on Geology* (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 152), which totals 114 pages, as well as *Instructions on Collecting Fossils*, again written by him. Undeniably interesting for anyone who has had the chance to have a look at the archive of Prof. Georgi Zlatarski is the unpublished *Atlas of Paleontology* (University Archive, fund 31, op. 1, archival unit 132) (Fig. 7). Within 33 pages, he goes to great lengths to draw and represent the characteristics of various fossils.

CONCLUDING NOTES

The privilege of processing, and thus experiencing, this unique documentary wealth was given to the author of this article, despite not being a scientist. In the modern world, where any information is available, any text can be photographed, copied or scanned, and thus stored, where no shortage of writing tools, writing and editing are technically easy, the work of our first scientists who made tremendous efforts to lift the development of Bulgarian science on a world level can be appreciated to an even greater extent. It is priceless to see closely among the documents of Prof. Zlatarski how he tried not to waste paper, but used every empty space and every available piece of paper (e.g., envelope, invitation, official form) to take notes; to see the beautiful and legible handwriting, every numbered page and the date of every lecture. The only thing that is felt is fascination with

the efforts made and the desire to preserve this for future generations. Many questions arise: how long it took him to write an autobiography, often in a foreign language (French, Croatian or Russian); how long it took him to translate from these languages the scientific literature vital to his work; how he made carefully, without mistakes, cross-outs or smudges, all the sketches and notes during his field trips? At the time when Prof. Zlatarski lived, typewriters were not popular in Bulgaria, therefore only original handwritten documents can be found in his personal archive. The only exception are a few reprints of his studies published in the Annual of Sofia University. The archivists who process these documents are, in most cases, the only people who have the opportunity to look in detail at the complete work of scientists and to see the complete work of an individual, which makes this work very interesting and exciting.

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